

Title: “Assessing the Effectiveness of Career Guidance on Career Planning Among Junior High Students in Riyadh Saudi Arabia”

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Declaration of Conflict

The researcher declared no conflicts of interest in this study. The researcher had no financial, personal, or professional interests that could have influenced the results and guaranteed that all aspects of the research, including data collection, analysis, and reporting, were carried out objectively and with integrity.